

ON CERTAIN DIOPHANTINE EQUATIONS INVOLVING TRIANGULAR NUMBERS

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Abstract

By the theory of the Pell equation, we study the polynomial solutions and positive integer solutions of certain Diophantine equations involving triangular numbers.

1. Introduction

A triangular number is a positive integer of the form

$$t_n = \binom{n}{2} = \frac{n(n-1)}{2}, \quad n \geq 2, \quad n \in \mathbb{Z}.$$

It is a classical result that all positive integer solutions of the Pythagorean equation

$$X^2 + Y^2 = Z^2 \tag{1.1}$$

are given by

$$X = 2kuv, \quad Y = k(u^2 - v^2), \quad Z = k(u^2 + v^2),$$

where k is a positive integer and u, v are co-prime positive integers of different parity with $u > v$. The solution (X, Y, Z) is called a Pythagorean triple.

In 1962, Sierpiński [6] showed that Equation (1.1) has infinitely many positive integer solutions $X = t_x, Y = t_y, Z = z$ with $\gcd(t_x, t_y) > 1$. In other words, he proved that the Diophantine equation

$$z^2 = t_x^2 + t_y^2 \tag{1.2}$$

has infinitely many positive integer solutions. As pointed out by Sierpiński [6], Schinzel showed that the set of positive integer solutions of Equation (1.2) with $\gcd(t_x, t_y) = 1$ is infinite. In 2008, Ulas [8] proved that Equation (1.2) has infinitely many polynomial solutions $x(t), y(t), z(t) \in \mathbb{Z}[t]$. By the theory of the Pell equation, we give another proof of Ulas' result in the following theorem.

Theorem 1.1. *Equation (1.2) has infinitely many polynomial solutions $x(t), y(t), z(t) \in \mathbb{Z}[t]$.*

In 2010, Ulas and Togbé [7] considered the rational solutions of the Diophantine equations

$$z^2 = f(x)^2 \pm f(y)^2, \tag{1.3}$$

where $f(x)$ are quadratic and cubic polynomials. In 2010, He, Togbé and Ulas [3] further investigated the integer solutions of Equation (1.3) for some special polynomials $f(x)$. They gave infinitely many integer solutions of the Diophantine equation

$$z^2 = (x^2 + a)^2 - (y^2 + a)^2$$

for some special values of a . When $a = -1$, the above Diophantine equation reduces to

$$Z^2 = t_X^2 - t_Y^2,$$

where $Z = z/8, X = (x - 1)/2, Y = (y - 1)/2$. Then there are infinitely many Pythagorean triangles (a Pythagorean triangle is a right triangle with integer side lengths) with a leg and the hypotenuse that are triangular numbers. We shall give a new proof of this result.

Theorem 1.2. *The Diophantine equation*

$$t_z^2 = x^2 + t_y^2 \tag{1.4}$$

has infinitely many polynomial solutions $x(t), y(t), z(t) \in \mathbb{Z}[t]$.

In 2004, Rakaczki [5] studied the integer solutions of the Diophantine equation

$$F\left(\binom{x}{n}\right) = b\binom{y}{m}, x \geq n, y \geq m, \tag{1.5}$$

where $F(x)$ is a polynomial with integer coefficients, $m (\geq 2)$ and n are positive integers, and b is a non-zero integer.

Motivated by Equations (1.2) and (1.5), we consider the positive integer solutions of the general Diophantine equation

$$z^2 = at_x^2 + bt_x t_y + ct_y^2, \tag{1.6}$$

where a, b, c are integers with $b^2 - 4ac \neq 0$. When $a = 1, b = 0, c = \pm 1$, Equation (1.6) reduces to Equations (1.2) and (1.4). By the theory of the Pell equation, we

$d(t)$	$x(t), y(t)$
$t^2 - 1$	$(t, 1)$
$t^2 \pm 2$	$(t^2 \pm 1, t)$
$9t^2 \pm 8t + 2$	$((9t \pm 4)^2 + 1, 3(9t \pm 4))$
$49t^2 \pm 20t + 2$	$((49t \pm 10)^2 - 1, 7(49t \pm 10))$
$t(t^3 \pm 2)$	$(t^3 \pm 1, t)$
$t(r^2t \pm 1), r \in \mathbb{Z}^+$	$(2r^2t \pm 1, 2r)$
$t(r^2t \pm 2), r \in \mathbb{Z}^+$	$(r^2t \pm 1, r)$

Table 1: An integer solution of the Pell equation $x^2 - d(t)y^2 = 1$

get the following results. In order to illustrate Theorem 1.3, we give an integer solution of the Pell equation $x^2 - d(t)y^2 = 1$ in Table 1.

For some special values of a, b, c , we have the following theorem.

Theorem 1.3. *Let $a = 1, b = 0, c + 1 = d(t)$, or $a = 1, b = 2, c + 3 = d(t)$, or $a = 1, b \neq 2 (b + 2 > 0$ is not a perfect square), $c = 1$. Then Equation (1.6) has infinitely many positive integer solutions.*

For general values of a, b, c , we obtain the following result.

Theorem 1.4. *Let $a = (2t + 1)^2(r^2(2t + 1)^2 - s)$, $b = -2r^2(2t + 1)^2 + s$, $c = r^2$, or $a = (2t + 1)^2(r^2(2t + 1)^2 - 2s(2t^2 + 2t + 1))$, $b = -2r^2(2t + 1)^2 + s(8t^2 + 8t + 3)$, $c = r^2 - s$, where r, s, t are positive integers. If $st(t + 1)$ is not a perfect square, then Equation (1.6) has infinitely many positive integer solutions.*

Lastly, we investigate the positive integer solutions of the related Diophantine equation

$$t_z = at_x^2 + bt_x t_y + ct_y^2, \tag{1.7}$$

where a, b, c are integers with $a^2 + b^2 + c^2 \neq 0$. When $a = 1, b = c = 0$, the only positive integer solutions of Equation (1.7) are $(z, x) = (1, 1), (2, 2), (9, 4)$ (see [2, 4]).

By the same method of Theorem 1.4, we have the following result.

Theorem 1.5. *Let $a = \frac{1}{2}(2t + 1)^2(sr^2(r + 1)^2(2t + 1)^2 - 2)s$, $b = -(sr^2(r + 1)^2(2t + 1)^2 - 1)s$, $c = \frac{1}{2}s^2r^2(r + 1)^2$, where r, s, t are positive integers. If $2st(t + 1)$ is not a perfect square, then Equation (1.7) has infinitely many positive integer solutions.*

2. Proofs of the Theorems

Proof of Theorem 1.1. Let $y = 2tx + 1 - 2t$, where t is a parameter. Then Equation (1.2) can be written as the following equation:

$$\frac{1}{4}(x - 1)^2 ((16t^4 + 1)x^2 + 16(-2t^4 + t^3)x + 16t^4 - 16t^3 + 4t^2) = z^2.$$

Consider

$$(16t^4 + 1)x^2 + 16(-2t^4 + t^3)x + 16t^4 - 16t^3 + 4t^2 = s^2,$$

and put

$$X = (16t^4 + 1)x + 8(-2t^4 + t^3), \quad Y = s.$$

We get the Pell equation

$$X^2 - (16t^4 + 1)Y^2 = -4t^2(2t - 1)^2. \tag{2.1}$$

Equation (2.1) has a solution

$$(X', Y') = (8t^3(2t - 1), 2t(2t - 1)),$$

and $(X'', Y'') = (32t^4 + 1, 8t^2)$ is a solution of the Pell equation

$$X^2 - (16t^4 + 1)Y^2 = 1.$$

An infinite number of solutions of Equation (2.1) are given by

$$\begin{aligned} X_n + Y_n \sqrt{16t^4 + 1} &= \left(8t^3(2t - 1) + 2t(2t - 1)\sqrt{16t^4 + 1}\right) \\ &\times \left(32t^4 + 1 + 8t^2\sqrt{16t^4 + 1}\right)^n, \quad n \geq 0, \end{aligned}$$

which leads to

$$X_n = (32t^4 + 1)X_{n-1} + 8t^2(16t^4 + 1)Y_{n-1}, \quad Y_n = 8t^2X_{n-1} + (32t^4 + 1)Y_{n-1}.$$

So

$$\begin{cases} X_n = 2(32t^4 + 1)X_{n-1} - X_{n-2}, & X_0 = 8t^3(2t - 1), \\ & X_1 = 8t^3(2t - 1)(64t^4 + 3), \\ Y_n = 2(32t^4 + 1)Y_{n-1} - Y_{n-2}, & Y_0 = 2t(2t - 1), \\ & Y_1 = 2t(2t - 1)(64t^4 + 1). \end{cases}$$

Using the relation $X_n = 2(32t^4 + 1)X_{n-1} - X_{n-2}$ twice, we get

$$X_{n+1} = 2(2(32t^4 + 1)^2 - 1)X_{n-1} - X_{n-3}.$$

Replacing n by $2n$, we have the relation

$$X_{2n+1} = 2(2(32t^4 + 1)^2 - 1)X_{2n-1} - X_{2n-3},$$

which holds for $n \geq 2$. From $X = (16t^4 + 1)x + 8(-2t^4 + t^3)$, $Y = s$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} x_{2n+1} &= 2(2(32t^4 + 1)^2 - 1)x_{2n-1} - x_{2n-3} + 256t^4(-16t^4 + 8t^3), \\ s_{2n+1} &= 2(2(32t^4 + 1)^2 - 1)s_{2n-1} - s_{2n-3}, \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} x_1 &= 32t^3(2t - 1), \quad x_3 = 64t^3(2t - 1)(8t^2 - 4t + 1)(8t^2 + 4t + 1)(32t^4 + 1), \\ s_1 &= 2t(2t - 1)(64t^4 + 1), \quad s_3 = 2t(2t - 1)(262144t^{12} + 20480t^8 + 384t^4 + 1). \end{aligned}$$

Thus, Equation (1.2) has infinitely many polynomial solutions

$$\begin{aligned} x_{2n+1} &\in \mathbb{Z}[t], \\ y_{2n+1} &= 2tx_{2n+1} + 1 - 2t \in \mathbb{Z}[t], \\ z_{2n+1} &= \frac{1}{2}(x_{2n+1} - 1)s_{2n+1} \in \mathbb{Z}[t], \end{aligned}$$

where $n \geq 0$. □

Example 2.1. When $n = 0$, Equation (1.2) has a polynomial solution

$$\begin{aligned} x_1(t) &= 32t^3(2t - 1), \\ y_1(t) &= 128t^5 - 64t^4 - 2t + 1, \\ z_1(t) &= t(2t - 1)(8t^2 - 4t + 1)(8t^2 + 4t + 1)(64t^4 - 32t^3 - 1). \end{aligned}$$

Proof of Theorem 1.2. Let $z = 2ty + 1$, where t is a parameter. Then Equation (1.4) is equivalent to

$$\frac{1}{4}y^2((16t^4 - 1)y^2 + (16t^3 + 2)y + 4t^2 - 1) = x^2.$$

Letting $(16t^4 - 1)y^2 + (16t^3 + 2)y + 4t^2 - 1 = s^2$, then

$$((16t^4 - 1)y + 8t^3 + 1)^2 - (16t^4 - 1)s^2 = 4t^2(2t + 1)^2.$$

Putting $X = (16t^4 - 1)y + 8t^3 + 1$, $Y = s$, we get the Pell equation

$$X^2 - (16t^4 - 1)Y^2 = 4t^2(2t + 1)^2. \tag{2.2}$$

Note that $(X', Y') = (8t^3(2t + 1), 2t(2t + 1))$ is a solution of Equation (2.2) and $(X'', Y'') = (4t^2, 1)$ is a solution of the Pell equation

$$X^2 - (16t^4 - 1)Y^2 = 1.$$

An infinite number of solutions of Equation (2.2) are given by

$$\begin{aligned} X_n + Y_n\sqrt{16t^4 - 1} &= \left(8t^3(2t + 1) + 2t(2t + 1)\sqrt{16t^4 - 1}\right) \\ &\quad \times \left(4t^2 + \sqrt{16t^4 - 1}\right)^n, \quad n \geq 0. \end{aligned}$$

In a similar way as in the proof of Theorem 1.1, we can get infinitely many polynomial solutions. □

Proof of Theorem 1.3. 1) When $a = 1, b = 0$, let $y = x + 1$. Then Equation (1.6) becomes

$$\frac{1}{4}x^2 ((c + 1)x^2 + (2c - 2)x + c + 1) = z^2.$$

Letting $(c + 1)x^2 + (2c - 2)x + c + 1 = s^2$, we have

$$((c + 1)x + (c - 1))^2 - (c + 1)s^2 = -4c.$$

If $c + 1 = d(t) = t^2 - 1$ (the proofs of the remaining cases in Table 1 are similar to this one), then

$$((t^2 - 1)x + t^2 - 3)^2 - (t^2 - 1)s^2 = -4t^2 + 8.$$

Putting $X = (t^2 - 1)x + t^2 - 3, Y = s$, we get the Pell equation

$$X^2 - (t^2 - 1)Y^2 = -4t^2 + 8. \tag{2.3}$$

Let us observe that the pair $(X', Y') = (-2, 2)$ is a solution of Equation (2.3). Moreover, the pair $(X'', Y'') = (t, 1)$ solves the Pell equation $X^2 - (t^2 - 1)Y^2 = 1$. An infinite number of positive integer solutions of Equation (2.3) are given by

$$X_n + Y_n\sqrt{t^2 - 1} = \left(-2 + 2\sqrt{t^2 - 1}\right) \left(t + \sqrt{t^2 - 1}\right)^n, \quad n \geq 0.$$

The remaining part of the proof is similar to the earlier ones for Theorems 1.1 and 1.2.

2) When $a = 1, b = 2$, put $y = x + 1$. Then Equation (1.6) can be reformulated in the form

$$\frac{1}{4}x^2 ((c + 3)x^2 + (2c - 2)x + c - 1) = z^2.$$

Taking $(c + 3)x^2 + (2c - 2)x + c - 1 = s^2$, we obtain Pell equation

$$((c + 3)x + (c - 1))^2 - (c + 3)s^2 = -4c + 4.$$

If $c + 3 = d(t) = t^2 - 1$ (the proofs of other cases in Table 1 are similar to this one), we have

$$((t^2 - 1)x + t^2 - 5)^2 - (t^2 - 1)s^2 = -4t^2 + 20.$$

Letting $X = (t^2 - 1)x + t^2 - 5, Y = s$, then

$$X^2 - (t^2 - 1)Y^2 = -4t^2 + 20. \tag{2.4}$$

It is easy to see that the pair $(X', Y') = (-4, 2)$ is a solution of Equation (2.4), and the pair $(X'', Y'') = (t, 1)$ solves the Pell equation $X^2 - (t^2 - 1)Y^2 = 1$. So an infinite number of positive integer solutions of Equation (2.4) are given by

$$X_n + Y_n\sqrt{t^2 - 1} = \left(-4 + 2\sqrt{t^2 - 1}\right) \left(t + \sqrt{t^2 - 1}\right)^n, \quad n \geq 0.$$

The remaining part of the proof is similar to the earlier ones.

3) When $a = 1, b \neq 2, c = 1$, take $y = x - 1$. Then Equation (1.6) is equal to

$$\frac{1}{4}(x - 1)^2 ((b + 2)x^2 - 2(b + 2)x + 4) = z^2.$$

Let us consider

$$(b + 2)x^2 - 2(b + 2)x + 4 = s^2,$$

which is equivalent to the Pell equation

$$X^2 - (b + 2)Y^2 = b^2 - 4, \tag{2.5}$$

where

$$X = (b + 2)x - (b + 2), \quad Y = s.$$

If $b + 2 > 0$ is not a perfect square, then the Pell equation

$$X^2 - (b + 2)Y^2 = 1$$

has infinitely many positive integer solutions. Let (u, v) be the least positive integer solution of $X^2 - (b + 2)Y^2 = 1$. And $(X_0, Y_0) = (b + 2, 2)$ is a positive integer solution of Equation (2.5). An infinite number of positive integer solutions of Equation (2.5) are given by

$$X_n + Y_n\sqrt{b + 2} = (b + 2 + 2\sqrt{b + 2}) (u + v\sqrt{b + 2})^n, \quad n \geq 0.$$

The remaining part of the proof is similar to the earlier ones. □

Proof of Theorem 1.4. 1) When $a = (2t + 1)^2(r^2(2t + 1)^2 - s)$, $b = -2r^2(2t + 1)^2 + s$, $c = r^2$, let $y = (2t + 1)x - t$. Then Equation (1.6) reduces to

$$\frac{1}{4}t(t + 1) (sx^2 - sx + r^2t(t + 1)) = z^2.$$

Letting

$$Z = 4z, \quad X = 2x - 1,$$

we get the Pell equation

$$Z^2 - st(t + 1)X^2 = 4r^2t^2(t + 1)^2 - st(t + 1). \tag{2.6}$$

If $st(t + 1)$ is not a perfect square, then the Pell equation

$$Z^2 - st(t + 1)X^2 = 1$$

has infinitely many positive integer solutions. Let (u, v) be the least positive integer solution of $Z^2 - st(t + 1)X^2 = 1$. Note that $(Z_0, X_0) = (2rt(t + 1), 1)$ is a positive

integer solution of Equation (2.6). An infinite number of positive integer solutions of Equation (2.6) are given by

$$Z_n + X_n \sqrt{st(t+1)} = \left(2rt(t+1) + \sqrt{st(t+1)}\right) \left(u + v\sqrt{st(t+1)}\right)^n, \quad n \geq 0,$$

which leads to

$$Z_n = uZ_{n-1} + vst(t+1)X_{n-1}, \quad X_n = vZ_{n-1} + uX_{n-1}.$$

Thus,

$$\begin{cases} Z_n = 2uZ_{n-1} - Z_{n-2}, & Z_0 = 2rt(t+1), \quad Z_1 = t(t+1)(2ru + sv), \\ X_n = 2uX_{n-1} - X_{n-2}, & X_0 = 1, \quad X_1 = 2rt(t+1)v + u. \end{cases}$$

From

$$z = \frac{Z}{4}, \quad x = \frac{X+1}{2},$$

we have

$$\begin{cases} z_n = 2uz_{n-1} - z_{n-2}, & z_0 = \frac{rt(t+1)}{2}, \quad z_1 = \frac{(2ru + sv)t(t+1)}{4}, \\ x_n = 2ux_{n-1} - x_{n-2} - u + 1, & x_0 = 1, \quad x_1 = rt(t+1)v + \frac{u+1}{2}. \end{cases}$$

According to the above relations and $2|t(t+1)$, we have

$$z_{2n} \in \mathbb{Z}^+, \quad x_{2n} \in \mathbb{Z}^+, \quad n \geq 1.$$

Thus, for $a = (2t+1)^2(r^2(2t+1)^2 - s)$, $b = -2r^2(2t+1)^2 + s$, $c = r^2$, if $st(t+1)$ is not a perfect square, Equation (1.6) has infinitely many positive integer solutions

$$(x, y, z) = (x_{2n}, (2t+1)x_{2n} - t, z_{2n}),$$

where $n \geq 1$.

2) We can obtain the result in a similar way like in case 1). □

Example 2.2. When $r = 1, s = 1$, we have

$$(a, b, c) = (4t(t+1)(2t+1)^2, -8t^2 - 8t - 1, 1).$$

For a given positive integer t , Equation (1.6) has infinitely many positive integer solutions (x_n, y_n, z_n) , which satisfy

$$\begin{cases} x_n = 2(2t+1)x_{n-1} - x_{n-2} - 2t, & x_0 = 1, \quad x_1 = (t+1)(2t+1), \\ y_n = (2t+1)x_n - t, \\ z_n = 2(2t+1)z_{n-1} - z_{n-2}, & z_0 = \frac{t(t+1)}{2}, \quad z_1 = t(t+1)^2. \end{cases}$$

Proof of Theorem 1.5. 1) When $a = \frac{1}{2}(2t + 1)^2(sr^2(r + 1)^2(2t + 1)^2 - 2)s$, $b = -(sr^2(r + 1)^2(2t + 1)^2 - 1)s$, $c = \frac{1}{2}s^2r^2(r + 1)^2$, let $y = (2t + 1)x - t$. Then Equation (1.7) becomes

$$2st(t + 1)x^2 - 2st(t + 1)x + r^2t^2(t + 1)^2(r + 1)^2s^2 + 1 = (2z - 1)^2.$$

Taking

$$Z = 4z - 2, \quad X = 2x - 1,$$

we get the Pell equation

$$Z^2 - 2st(t + 1)X^2 = 4(rst(t + 1)(r + 1) + 1)^2 - 2st(t + 1)(2r + 1)^2. \quad (2.7)$$

If $2st(t + 1)$ is not a perfect square, then the Pell equation

$$Z^2 - 2st(t + 1)X^2 = 1$$

has infinitely many positive integer solutions. Let (u, v) be the least positive integer solution of $Z^2 - 2st(t + 1)X^2 = 1$. And $(Z_0, X_0) = (2(rst(t + 1)(r + 1) + 1), 2r + 1)$ is a positive integer solution of Equation (2.7). An infinite number of positive integer solutions of Equation (2.7) are given by

$$\begin{aligned} Z_n + X_n\sqrt{2st(t + 1)} &= \left(2(rst(t + 1)(r + 1) + 1) + (2r + 1)\sqrt{2st(t + 1)}\right) \\ &\times \left(u + v\sqrt{2st(t + 1)}\right)^n, \quad n \geq 0. \end{aligned}$$

The remaining part of the proof can be obtained in a way similar to that of Theorem 1.4. □

3. A Remark and Question on Equation (1.7)

Taking $(a, b, c) = (1, 2, 1)$ in Equation (1.7), we have

$$t_z = (t_x + t_y)^2.$$

Considering $t_z = w^2$, we obtain

$$Z^2 - 2W^2 = 1,$$

where

$$Z = 2z - 1, \quad W = 2w.$$

From

$$Z_n + W_n\sqrt{2} = \left(3 + 2\sqrt{2}\right)^n, \quad n \geq 1,$$

we get

$$Z_n = \frac{\varepsilon^n + \bar{\varepsilon}^n}{2}, \quad W_n = \frac{\varepsilon^n - \bar{\varepsilon}^n}{2\sqrt{2}},$$

where $\varepsilon = 3 + 2\sqrt{2}$, $\bar{\varepsilon} = 3 - 2\sqrt{2}$. Thus,

$$z_n = \frac{\varepsilon^n + \bar{\varepsilon}^n + 2}{4}, \quad w_n = \frac{\varepsilon^n - \bar{\varepsilon}^n}{4\sqrt{2}}.$$

It is easy to show that z_n and w_n are positive integers. Then we need to study the positive integer solutions of

$$w_n = t_x + t_y.$$

Solving it for y , we have

$$y = \frac{1 + \sqrt{-(2x - 1)^2 + 8w_n + 2}}{2}. \tag{3.1}$$

By some numerical calculations, we get several positive integer solutions of Equation (3.1) in Table 2 in the range $1 \leq n \leq 100$ and $1 \leq x \leq 10^7$.

n	(x, y)
1	(2, 1)
2	(3, 3), (4, 1)
8	(61, 684), (459, 511)
10	(678, 3942), (723, 3934)
12	(12726, 19530), (15831, 17110)
14	(23496, 133812), (61491, 121147)
16	(530868, 587532)
17	(28864, 1911458), (598862, 1815453)

Table 2: Some positive integer solutions of Equation (3.1)

Maybe we could get more positive integer solutions in the large range. However, we were not able to give a positive answer to the following question.

Question 3.1. Are there finitely many positive integer solutions of Equation (3.1)?

A similar remark can be made for the case

$$t_z = (at_x + bt_y)^2.$$

There are some papers (see [1] and the related references) that studied the X -coordinates of the Pell equations as a special number or the sum (or product) of two special numbers, and obtained some finiteness results. But it seems that the methods are not applicable here for our case.

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